

Philippine traditional herbal remedies for hypertension

Meliza Parba, Cesar G. Demayo

Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science and Mathematics, Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology, Iligan City, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 31, 2024

Revised Dec 27, 2024

Accepted Mar 6, 2025

Keywords:

Decoction
Medicinal plants
Philippines
Province
Region

ABSTRACT

Certain areas of the Philippines continue to rely on traditional non-pharmacological approaches, such as herbal medicine, for hypertension treatment, a significant public health problem globally. Therefore, a systematic review of plants used in the Philippines to treat hypertension, based on the PRISMA flow diagram, was carried out. Relevant ethnobotanical studies were retrieved from databases such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and PubMed. Following the eligibility screening, 36 ethnobotanical studies were included. The majority of the studies included in this review came from Region XIII (CARAGA), Region VI (Western Visayas), and Region X (Northern Mindanao). The most prevalent plant family and species were Poaceae (12 species) and *Cymbopogon citratus* (DC.) Stapf. (16 citations), respectively. Leaves were the most common plant parts utilized while decoction was the most frequently mentioned mode of preparation. Oral administration was the most widely used form of administration. This review highlights medicinal plants with potential antihypertensive properties. It underscores the need to conduct a systematic review of their pharmacological properties to determine which have been scientifically validated and are most effective against hypertension.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Meliza Parba

Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science and Mathematics,
Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology

Iligan City, Philippines

Email: meliza.parba@g.msuiit.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

Ischemic heart disease continues to be the leading cause of death in the Philippines in the first half of 2023 [1]. One of the major risk factors for this disease is hypertension (HTN), commonly known as high blood pressure. The 2020 Philippine Society for Hypertension clinical practice guideline defines hypertension as an office blood pressure (BP) of 140/90 mmHg or higher, recorded at least twice on two separate days [2]. In 2005, Kearney *et al.* [3] forecasted that the number of adults with hypertension worldwide would increase to approximately 1.56 billion in the year 2025. Although the exact causes of hypertension are unknown, several contributing factors have been identified that may increase susceptibility to developing hypertension. These include smoking, obesity, high sodium intake, or a sedentary lifestyle [4].

The treatment for hypertension involves both non- and pharmacological methods. Non-pharmacological methods include a change in lifestyle that addresses the risk factors [5] and is considered the first step in managing hypertension. On the other hand, pharmacological approaches involve the use of various drugs, belonging to different classes, to control blood pressure. These include diuretics, sympathomimetic agents, renin, and angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs), calcium channel, α -adrenergic, and β -adrenergic blockers, and vasodilators [6]. However, a significant portion

of the population in the Philippines lacks the privilege of consulting a professional healthcare provider [7], forcing them to continually rely on traditional non-pharmacological approaches such as herbal medicines.

Plants have a long history of use for the treatment of various diseases [8], including hypertension [9]. Several clinical trials have been conducted worldwide to evaluate the antihypertensive properties of medicinal plants. For example, powdered leaves of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* and *Olea europaea* were found to have comparable antihypertensive efficacy and safety to captopril, a common antihypertensive drug [10]. Another clinical trial reported significant reductions in systolic, diastolic, and mean arterial pressures of subjects treated with *Mentha longifolia*, *Viola odorata*, and *Urtica dioica*, which were dependent on the dose and duration of the treatment [11]. The results of these studies highlight the promising potential of plants as a source of pharmaceutical drugs for hypertension.

Currently, ten medicinal plants are endorsed by the Department of Health (DOH) and have been thoroughly tested and clinically proven by the Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care (PITAHC) as alternative medicines for certain conditions [12]. However, none of these plants has been approved for the treatment of hypertension. Additionally, there are no published articles on the compilation of plant species specifically used for the treatment of hypertension. Previous publications have focused on other health issues such as cancer or tumors [13], gynecologic diseases [14], anemia [12], and obstetric care [15]. Hence, this study aims to address this gap by determining the medicinal plants used for treating hypertension in the Philippines and providing a list of potential plants to be validated that could be used to develop future hypertension treatments. In this systematic review, we also identified the most common plant parts, modes of preparation, and administration used to treat hypertension in the Philippines.

2. METHOD

This study is a systematic review of medicinal plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines. This is conducted based on Preferred Reporting Items For Systematic Reviews And Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram [16], as shown in Figure 1. This diagram provides a visual representation of the study selection process, which records the number of studies identified, screened, and included, and the reasons for exclusion at each stage of the review.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart of the study

2.1. Data sources and search strategy

The materials used in this study were obtained from three electronic databases: Science Direct (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>), Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>), PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). Key search terms used included: “ethnomedicine,” “ethnobotany,” “medicinal plants,” “traditional medicine,” “hypertension,” “high blood,” “highblood,” “alternative medicine,” and “Philippines”.

2.2. Study selection criteria

Studies written in English or Filipino and published until May 2024 were considered. Observational studies were also specifically selected as they provide primary information about ethnobotanical knowledge [12],

[14], reflecting how the communities in the Philippines are using these medicinal plants for the treatment of hypertension. Other types of articles, such as systematic reviews, literature reviews, and correspondence, were excluded.

2.3. Data extraction

The full text of all the eligible studies was retrieved. All irrelevant articles were excluded, and reasons for their exclusion were recorded. From each eligible study, the following data were collected: first author, year of publication, plant family, plant species, plant part used, mode of preparation, administration, informants, and place of study.

2.4. Data analysis

The results of this study were organized and presented using tables and graphs generated in Microsoft Excel. This provides a summary of the key findings, allowing for easier interpretation. A map was also created to determine the geographical distribution of ethnobotanical studies included in the systematic review.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This is the first systematic review of medicinal plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines. As depicted in Figure 1, the initial literature search resulted in 232 ethnobotanical studies, of which 17 were duplicates. Following eligibility screening, 179 studies were excluded and 36 studies were included.

3.1. Geographical distribution of studies

Figure 2 shows the geographical distribution of ethnobotanical studies with data on plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines and the informants cited per region. The numbers represent the studies conducted in each region. These studies originated from different provinces in the Philippines, covering fifteen regions. Twenty-five percent of these studies came from Region XIII (CARAGA), where most respondents belong to the Manobo and Mamanwa Tribes, respectively. Region XIII (CARAGA) was followed by Region VI (Western Visayas) and Region X (Northern Mindanao), with four (11.11%) ethnobotanical studies each, as illustrated in Figure 2 and Table 1. These regions contain diverse plant species used to treat diseases and are known for the presence of Indigenous communities with traditional knowledge of medicinal plants [17]. Additionally, these areas are usually remote and disadvantaged [14]; thus, access to medications and healthcare professionals is difficult, leading people to rely on medicinal plants to treat diseases including hypertension.

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of the ethnobotanical studies with data on plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines, indicating the number of studies conducted and the informants cited per region

Table 1. Synthesis of the studies with data on plants used for hypertension in the Philippines

Author	Province	Informants	Sample Size	Number of plant species used for hypertension
[18]	Batanes	Locals	112	9
[19]	Bataan	Kanawan Aytas	61	2
[20]	Agusan del Sur	Manobo	39	1
[21]	Ifugao	Kalanguya tribe	125	4
[22]	Benguet	Locals	47	1
[23]	Aurora	Ilongot-Egongot community	65	6
[24]	Albay	Locals	74	3
[25]	Leyte	Locals with home garden	171	2
[26]	South Cotabato	T'boli	28	1
[27]	Iloilo	Locals	111	13
[28]	Cavite	Local herbalists	106	9
[29]	Aklan	Ati Tribe	106	2
[30]	Antique	Locals	16	1
[31]	Agusan del Sur	Manobos	122	20
[32]	Laguna	Local patients	15	10
[33]	Metro Manila	Residents	32	2
[34]	Surigao del Sur	Residents	65	1
[35]	Surigao del Sur	Residents	35	1
[36]	Davao del Sur	Matigsalug Tribe	35	1
[37]	Zamboanga del Norte, del Sur, and Sibugay	Bajau	36	2
[38]	Agusan del Norte and Surigao del Norte	Mamanwa Tribe	15	1
[39]	Surigao del Sur	Locals	46	2
[40]	South Cotabato and Sarangani	Obo, T'boli, Blaan and Tagakaolo	136	1
[41]	Surigao and Agusan del Norte	Mamanwa Tribe	78	2
[42]	Bukidnon	Talaandig Tribe	66	3
[43]	Misamis Occidental	Subanen Healers	60	1
[44]	Lanao del Norte	Higaonon Tribe	62	5
[45]	Lanao del Norte	Muslim Meranaos	122	12
[46]	Guimaras	Ati Negrito	142	12
[47]	Bataan	Aetas	77	2
[48]	Agusan del Sur	Manobo Tribe	40	2
[49]	Surigao del Sur	Manobos	66	2
[50]	Zamboanga del Sur	Subanen Tribe	89	7
[51]	Kalinga	Locals	80	4
[52]	Oriental Mindoro	Mangyan	114	4
[53]	Bohol	Eskaya Traditional Healers	85	22

3.2. Most common plant families and species used to treat hypertension in the Philippines

A total of 44 plant families and 86 species were recorded as being used for the treatment of hypertension. Figure 3 presents the most commonly reported (a) families and (b) species of plants used in the Philippines. Among all plant families reported, the most represented was Poaceae, with 12 species mentioned for the treatment of hypertension, as depicted in Figure 3(a). The dominance of Poaceae, also known as the grass family, can be attributed to its being one of the most important flowering plant families, with a vast distribution and abundance [54]. Family Poaceae is composed of 789 genera and 11,783 species belonging to 12 subfamilies and 54 tribes [55]. Plant families with high species richness have been reported to have more useful species [56]. Additionally, Asteraceae is one of the second families with the greatest number of representative species used to treat hypertension. A review of medicinal plants for hypertension therapy in Iran [57] and South Africa [58] also listed the highest number of medicinal plants from the Asteraceae family.

Figure 3(b) shows that the most frequently mentioned plant species is *Cymbopogon citratus* (DC.) Stapf. with 16 records. This finding differs from the results of other systematic reviews, such as those conducted globally [9] and in Nigeria [59]. These differences in species utilization could be the result of diverse social and cultural backgrounds, which greatly influence medicinal practices across different countries [60]. They could also be attributed to the differences in each geographical area in terms of environmental factors, such as climate, soil fertility, and soil salinity, which affect the phytochemical composition of medicinal plants [61]. Lastly, these differences can be due to the availability of the same medicinal plants in these areas. On the other hand, *Allium sativum* L., the third most frequently cited species in the Philippines, is also reported by [4], [59] as the most mentioned plant species for treating hypertension. This commonality across different countries may indicate the potential of *Allium sativum* L. as a potent remedy for hypertension.

Figure 3. Most common: (a) families and (b) species of plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines

Several studies have reported the antihypertensive properties of the bioactive compounds in medicinal plants included in this review, particularly those of the frequently mentioned species. *Cymbopogon citratus* (DC.) Stapf and citral, the major constituent of this plant, exhibit vasorelaxant effects *ex vivo* by facilitating the secretion of endothelial vasodilators and blocking calcium channels [62]. In addition, another essential oil constituent from *C. citratus* (DC.) Stapf is citronellol, which acts in the same manner as citral when evaluated on rats [63]. Moreover, [64] reported that aqueous extracts of *Annona muricata* L. fruit parts (pericarp, pulp, and seed) inhibit angiotensin-I converting enzyme (ACE) *in vitro*, which could be attributed to their phenolic contents. On the other hand, allicin is the most abundant compound in raw *A. sativum* L. [65]. Allicin has been reported to exhibit an antihypertensive effect through vasodilatory properties and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) mechanisms in spontaneously hypertensive rats [66]. These findings suggest the potential of these medicinal plants as an alternative for managing hypertension.

3.3. Most common plant parts, mode of preparation, and administration of medicinal plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines

Figure 4 illustrates the most common 4(a) plant parts, 4(b) mode of preparation, and 4(c) administration of medicinal plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines. As shown in Figure 4(a), the most common plant part used for herbal preparations was leaves (45 records). Similar findings with leaves as the most commonly used plant parts have been recorded by other systematic reviews [9], [67]. The high usage of leaves might be explained by the abundance of compounds found in leaves, which serve as sites for the synthesis of secondary metabolites [68]. These secondary metabolites contribute to a variety of plant bioactivities and are the active components of most herbal preparations [18], [28]. Additionally, leaves are widely available and are common plant parts, especially in tropical countries, such as the Philippines [27]. This also ensures sustainability in the use of medicinal plants compared to other plant parts, as leaves can regenerate quickly, unlike other parts such as roots and stems [69]. The excessive use of fruits and seeds also has negative impacts on plant genetic diversity and distribution owing to their role in sexual reproduction and dispersal [70].

Filipinos use various methods to prepare medicinal plants for the management of hypertension. As illustrated in Figure 4(b), the most frequently used mode of medicinal preparation was decoction, with 60 plant species prepared this way. This result is in congruence with other systematic reviews [9], [67]. Both previous studies reported that the common mode of medicinal preparation was decoction. Decoction is known to be one of the simplest and oldest herbal preparations [28], which involves boiling plant materials for a certain period. According to [71], [72], using heat on aqueous extracts accelerates biological reactions and the extraction of

bioactive components. In a randomized clinical trial assessing the effectiveness of two medicinal plants in galenic forms of tablets and decoction for hypertension treatment, the decoction was more effective than tablets. This result could be due to the higher absorption of bioactive compounds when prepared in this manner [73].

Furthermore, based on Figure 4(c), the major route of administration was oral, accounting for 102 species ingested in various ways, including drinking (70 species), eating (30 species), using as a spice in cooking, and by taking as a pill (1 species each). Oral administration is mostly preferred due to advantages like high patient compliance, convenient administration, and minimal preparation [74]. The prevalence of oral administration may also be attributed to the higher efficacy of plant-healing agents when taken internally [75].

Figure 4. Most common: (a) plant parts, (b) mode of preparation, and (c) administration of medicinal plants used to treat hypertension in the Philippines

This review identifies common plants, plant parts, modes of preparation, and administration utilized by Indigenous and local users in the Philippines for treating hypertension. This implies the essential role of plants as a vital source of medicine in the Philippines, especially for people in remote areas with limited and no access to modern health services. This review may help promote the conservation of valuable plant species and the geographical areas where these plant species thrive, as medicinal plants are increasingly threatened due to habitat destruction resulting from industrialization and climate change, as modernization progresses [17].

The findings of this study may provide a list of potential plants that can be scientifically validated for the treatment of hypertension, ultimately leading to drug development.

This study has several limitations. Observational studies with data on medicinal plants for treating hypertension have only come from fifteen regions in the Philippines. This suggests the possibility of undocumented medicinal plants in other regions that may be useful for treating hypertension. Additionally, this review mainly focused on the plant species, family, locale of the study, plant part used, mode of preparation, and administration. Another systematic review must be done on the pharmacological properties of these plant species to know which have been validated and are most effective against hypertension. Lastly, toxicological studies are needed to determine and verify the safety of these medicinal plants in treating hypertension.

4. CONCLUSION

This study presents data on medicinal plants used in the Philippines to treat hypertension. Eighty-six plant species belonging to forty-four families were reported, retrieved from 36 ethnobotanical studies included after the eligibility screening. The findings of this study imply that medicinal plants have been used for treating hypertension, highlighting the need to provide a scientific basis for these medicinal plants. Consequently, this review can be used as a reference list to help discover alternative therapeutic options for treating hypertension. Lastly, pharmacological and toxicological studies should be conducted to ensure the efficacy and safety of medicinal plants used for hypertension treatment in the Philippines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the Department of Science and Technology - Accelerated Science and Technology Human Resource Development Program (DOST-ASTHRDP) for the financial assistance, as well as the Center of Integrative Health, Premier Research Institute of Science and Mathematics (PRISM) at Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology for providing the necessary support needed to complete this study.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This study is funded by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) through the Accelerated Science and Technology Human Resource Program (ASTHRDP).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Meliza Parba	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓
Cesar G. Demayo	✓	✓		✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	✓

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [MP], upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] PSA, "2023 Causes of Deaths in the Philippines (Provisional as of 30 September 2023)," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://psa.gov.ph/content/2023-causes-deaths-philippines-preliminary-31-july-2023>. Accessed: June 25, 2024.
- [2] D. I. D. Ona *et al.*, "Executive summary of the 2020 clinical practice guidelines for the management of hypertension in the Philippines," *Journal of Clinical Hypertension*, vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 1637–1650, 2021, doi: 10.1111/jch.14335.
- [3] P. M. Kearney, M. Whelton, K. Reynolds, P. Muntner, P. K. Whelton, and J. He, "Global burden of hypertension: analysis of worldwide data," *The Lancet*, vol. 365, no. 9455, pp. 217–223, 2005, doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(05)17741-1.
- [4] M. A. Abdulazeez *et al.*, "A systematic review with meta-analysis on the antihypertensive efficacy of Nigerian medicinal plants," *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 279, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2021.114342.
- [5] J. Redon and R. Carmena, "Present and future of drug therapy in hypertension: an overview," *Blood Pressure*, vol. 33, no. 1, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1080/08037051.2024.2320401.
- [6] A. D. Sinha and R. Agarwal, "Clinical pharmacology of antihypertensive therapy for the treatment of hypertension in CKD," *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 757–764, May 2019, doi: 10.2215/CJN.04330418.
- [7] J. Sison, R. Divinagracia, and J. Nailles, "Asian management of hypertension: Current status, home blood pressure, and specific concerns in Philippines (a country report)," *The Journal of Clinical Hypertension*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 504–507, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1111/jch.13802.
- [8] H. I. A. Boy *et al.*, "Recommended medicinal plants as source of natural products: a review," *Digital Chinese Medicine*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 131–142, 2018, doi: 10.1016/S2589-3777(19)30018-7.
- [9] M. Z. Aumeeruddy and M. F. Mahomoodally, "Traditional herbal therapies for hypertension: A systematic review of global ethnobotanical field studies," *South African Journal of Botany*, vol. 135, pp. 451–464, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.sajb.2020.09.008.
- [10] N. Elkafrawy *et al.*, "Antihypertensive efficacy and safety of a standardized herbal medicinal product of Hibiscus sabdariffa and Olea europaea extracts (NW Roselle): A phase-II, randomized, double-blind, captopril-controlled clinical trial," *Phytotherapy Research*, vol. 34, no. 12, pp. 3379–3387, 2020, doi: 10.1002/ptr.6792.
- [11] A. A. Samaha, M. Fawaz, A. Salami, S. Baydoun, and A. H. Eid, "Antihypertensive indigenous lebanese plants: ethnopharmacology and a clinical trial," *Biomolecules*, vol. 9, no. 7, p. 292, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.3390/biom9070292.
- [12] M. C. Magtalas *et al.*, "Ethnomedicinal plants used for the prevention and treatment of anemia in the Philippines: a systematic review," *Tropical Medicine and Health*, vol. 51, no. 1, p. 27, May 2023, doi: 10.1186/s41182-023-00515-x.
- [13] J. R. Pucot, M. M. E. Manting, and C. G. Demayo, "Ethnobotanical plants used by selected indigenous peoples of mindanao, the Philippines as cancer therapeutics," *Pharmacophore*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 61–69, 2019.
- [14] M. C. Magtalas *et al.*, "A systematic review of medicinal plants used in the treatment of gynecologic diseases in the Philippines," *Phytomedicine Plus*, vol. 3, no. 3, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.phyplu.2023.100462.
- [15] M. C. Magtalas *et al.*, "A systematic review of ethnomedicinal plants used for pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum care in the Philippines," *Phytomedicine Plus*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.phyplu.2023.100407.
- [16] M. J. Page *et al.*, "The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews," *Revista Panamericana de Salud Publica/Pan American Journal of Public Health*, vol. 46, 2022, doi: 10.26633/RPSP.2022.112.
- [17] M. L. Canceran *et al.*, "Ethnomedicinal plants of the Dumagat community of Paraiso, Culat, Casiguran, Aurora, Philippines," *International Journal of Biosciences (IJB)*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 261–267, 2021, doi: 10.12692/ijb/18.3.261-267.
- [18] R. Abe and K. Ohtani, "An ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants and traditional therapies on Batan Island, the Philippines," *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 145, no. 2, pp. 554–565, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2012.11.029.
- [19] N. C. B. Antonio and R. J. G. Tuason, "Ethnobotanical and phytochemical study of the medicinal plants used by Kanawan Aytas in Morong, Bataan, Philippines," *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, vol. 21, no. 3, 2022, doi: 10.56042/ijtk.v21i3.31614.
- [20] J. G. Arboleda, E. F. Gamalinda, L. A. Ombat, F. Jhun, and F. Almadin, "Ethnomedicinal study of animals and plants used by Agusanon Manobo in La Paz, Agusan del Sur, Philippines," *Annals of Studies in Science and Humanities*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 18–35, 2022.
- [21] T. D. Balangcod and A. K. D. Balangcod, "Ethnomedicinal knowledge of plants and healthcare practices among the Kalanguya tribe in Tinoc, Ifugao, Luzon, Philippines," *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 227–238, 2011.
- [22] T. D. Balangcod and K. D. Balangcod, "Plants and culture: Plant utilization among the local communities in Kabayan, Benguet Province, Philippines," *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 609–622, 2018.
- [23] A. N. Balberona, J. J. Noveno, M. G. B. Angeles, R. I. Santos, E. J. D. J. Cachin, and K. G. J. Cruz, "Ethnomedicinal plants utilized by the ilongot-egongot community of Bayanihan, Maria Aurora, Aurora, Philippines," *International Journal of Agricultural Technology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 145–159, 2018.
- [24] T. H. R. Belgica, M. D. Suba, and G. J. D. Alejandro, "Quantitative ethnobotanical study of medicinal flora used by local inhabitants in selected barangay of malinao, albay, philippines," *Biodiversitas*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 2711–2721, 2021, doi: 10.13057/biodiv/d220720.
- [25] B. Belonias, C. Platino, and J. Malanguis, "Agrobiodiversity of home gardens in selected marginal upland villages of Inopacan, Leyte, Philippines," *Annals of Tropical Research*, pp. 48–69, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.32945/atr36s4.2014.
- [26] J. R. Campilan, M. C. Tumamac, and E. L. Dorado, "Quantitative ethnobotanical study, phytochemical screening and antibacterial assay of ethnomedicinal plants of T'boli In Lemsnolon, Tboli, South Cotabato," *International Journal of Pharmacology, Phytochemistry and Ethnomedicine*, vol. 13, pp. 45–61, 2019, doi: 10.18052/www.scipress.com/ijppe.13.45.
- [27] C. S. Cordero, U. Meve, and G. J. D. Alejandro, "Ethnobotany and diversity of medicinal plants used among rural communities in Mina, Iloilo, Philippines: A quantitative study," *Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.japb.2022.12.003.
- [28] E. S. Caunca and L. O. Balinado, "The practice of using medicinal plants by local herbalists in cavite, philippines," *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 335–343, 2021, doi: 10.56042/ijtk.v20i2.26862.
- [29] C. Cordero, A. Ligsay, and G. Alejandro, "Ethnobotanical documentation of medicinal plants used by the Ati tribe in Malay, Aklan, Philippines," *Journal of Complementary Medicine Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 170, 2020, doi: 10.5455/jcmr.2020.11.01.20.
- [30] J. A. G. P. Dalisay, P. S. Bangcaya, and M. A. K. Naive, "Taxonomic studies and ethnomedicinal uses of zingiberaceae in the mountain ranges of Northern Antique, Philippines," *In Biological Forum—An International Journal*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 68–73, 2018.
- [31] M. L. G. Dapar, G. J. D. Alejandro, U. Meve, and S. Liede-Schumann, "Quantitative ethnopharmacological documentation and molecular confirmation of medicinal plants used by the Manobo tribe of Agusan del Sur, Philippines," *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 14, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s13002-020-00363-7.
- [32] R. R. Fiscal and A. C. C. Chavez, "Ethnobotanical profiling of commonly utilized plants for hypertension and diabetes in the Province of Laguna, Philippines," *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, vol. Volume 5, no. Issue 9, pp. 152–154, 2016, doi: 10.21275/ART20161424.
- [33] R. L. Flores *et al.*, "Ethnomedicinal study of plants sold in Quiapo, Manila, Philippines," *Scholars Academic Journal of Biosciences*, vol. 4, no. 4A, pp. 359–365, 2016, doi: 10.36347/sajb.2016.v04i04.012.

- [34] G. Gruyal, "Ethnomedicinal plants used by residents in Northern Surigao del Sur, Philippines," *Natural Products Chemistry & Research*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2014, doi: 10.4172/2329-6836.1000140.
- [35] G. A. Gruyal, J. Patero, M. T. A. Alas, V. B. Gruyal, and J. A. Intano, "Ethno medicinal plant identification and utilization in Ayoke Island, Cantilan Surigao del Sur, Philippines," *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 346–360, 2021.
- [36] C. P. B. Guevara and M. M. Garcia, "Ethnobotanical practices of matigsalug tribe on medicinal plants at Barangay Baganihan, Marilog District, Davao City," *Journal of Complementary and Alternative Medical Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1–14, 2018, doi: 10.9734/jocamr/2018/43031.
- [37] G. Madjos and K. Ramos, "Ethnobotany, systematic review and field mapping on folkloric medicinal plants in the Zamboanga Peninsula, Mindanao, Philippines," *Journal of Complementary Medicine Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 21, 2021, doi: 10.5455/jcmr.2021.12.01.05.
- [38] L. C. Mapatac, "Characterization of selected medicinal plants of Mamanwa Tribe in Caraga, Philippines," *Texila International Journal of Basic Medical Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 44–52, 2019, doi: 10.21522/tijbms.2016.04.01.art005.
- [39] J. C. Montero and D. T. Geducos, "Ethnomedicinal plants used by the local folks in two selected villages of San Miguel, Surigao del Sur, Mindanao, Philippines," *International Journal of Agricultural Technology*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 193–212, 2021.
- [40] M. L. Non-Cabrera, A. L. Descallar, C. D. G. Obemio, T. T. B. Martin-dela Cruz, and R. Lañojan, "Ethnomedicinal Resources of the Indigenous People's (IP) Groups in the SOCSARGEN Region," *Journal of Health Research and Society*, vol. 1, p. 2, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.34002/jhrs.v1i0.8.
- [41] O. M. Nuneza, B. C. Rodriguez, and J. G. M. Nasiad, "Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used by the mamanwa tribe of surigao del norte and agusan del norte, Mindanao, Philippines," *Biodiversitas*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 3284–3296, 2021, doi: 10.13057/BIODIV/D220634.
- [42] N. M. O. Odchimar, O. M. Nuneza, M. M. Uy, and W. T. Senarath, "Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used by the Talaandig Tribe in Brgy. Lilingayon, Valencia City, Bukidnon, Philippines," *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 358–364, 2017.
- [43] M. F. L. Olandag, "Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used by the Subanen healers of Mamalad, Calamba, Misamis Occidental," *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 37–59, 2020, doi: 10.7828/jmds.v9i2.1485.
- [44] L. F. Olowa, M. A. J. Torres, E. C. Aranico, and C. G. Demayo, "Medicinal plants used by the Higaonon tribe of Rogongon, Iligan City, Mindanao, Philippines," *Advances in Environmental Biology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1442–1449, 2012.
- [45] L. Olowa and C. G. Demayo, "Ethnobotanical uses of medicinal plants among the Muslim Maranaos in Iligan City, Mindanao, Philippines," *Advances in Environmental Biology*, vol. 9, no. 27, pp. 204–215, 2015.
- [46] H. G. Ong and Y.-D. Kim, "Quantitative ethnobotanical study of the medicinal plants used by the Ati Negrito indigenous group in Guimaras island, Philippines," *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 157, pp. 228–242, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2014.09.015.
- [47] C. G. C. Pablo, "Botika sa kalikasan: Medicinal plants used by Aetas of Sitio Parapal Hermosa Bataan, Philippines," *Journal of Social Health*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 101–127, 2019.
- [48] L. Dela Rosa Paraguison, D. N. Tandang, and G. J. Duran Alejandro, "Medicinal Plants used by the Manobo Tribe of Prosperidad, Agusan Del Sur, Philippinesan Ethnobotanical Survey," *Asian Journal of Biological and Life sciences*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 326–333, 2021, doi: 10.5530/ajbls.2020.9.49.
- [49] H. A. Pineda, S. T. Cortes, H. A. Pineda, and S. T. Cortes, "Inventory of ethnopharmacologically-significant plants used by the Manobos in Surigao del Sur, Philippines," *Journal of Agriculture and Technology Management*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 67–72, 2022.
- [50] J. R. L. Pizon, O. M. Nuñez, M. M. Uy, and W. T. P. S. K. Senarath, "Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used by the Subanen Tribe of Lapuyan, Zamboanga del Sur," *Bulletin of Environment, Pharmacology and Life Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 55, pp. 53–67, 2016.
- [51] M. Manuel, T. P. Banwa, M. E. Quesada, and C. L. Ammakiw, "Documentation of ethnomedicinal plants used by the subtribes of lower Kalinga province," vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 1193–1224, 2023.
- [52] R. R. Rubite, "Ethnopharmacologic documentation of selected Philippine ethnolinguistic groups: The Mangyan (Tadyawan) people of Mindoro Island," *University of the Philippines Manila*, 2002.
- [53] R. I. M. Teves, O. A. G. Tantengco, R. J. U. Sumatra, H. M. Carag, and J. S. Isidro-Lapeña, "Ethnomedicinal Survey of Valuable Plants Used by Eskaya Traditional Healers in Bohol Island, Philippines," *Acta Medica Philippina*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 17–26, 2023, doi: 10.47895/amp.vi0.3883.
- [54] F. Gebashe, A. O. Aremu, J. F. Finnie, and J. Van Staden, "Grasses in South African traditional medicine: A review of their biological activities and phytochemical content," *South African Journal of Botany*, vol. 122, pp. 301–329, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.sajb.2018.10.012.
- [55] R. J. Soreng *et al.*, "A worldwide phylogenetic classification of the Poaceae (Gramineae) III: An update," *Journal of Systematics and Evolution*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 476–521, 2022, doi: 10.1111/jse.12847.
- [56] M. V. Palchetti, F. Zamudio, S. Zeballos, A. Davies, G. E. Barboza, and M. A. Giorgis, "Large-scale patterns of useful native plants based on a systematic review of ethnobotanical studies in Argentina," *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 93–100, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.pecon.2023.04.001.
- [57] B. Baharvand-Ahmadi and M. Asadi-Samani, "A mini-review on the most important effective medicinal plants to treat hypertension in ethnobotanical evidence of Iran.," *Journal of nephropharmacology*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 3–8, 2017.
- [58] F. O. Balogun and A. O. T. Ashafa, "A Review of Plants Used in South African Traditional Medicine for the Management and Treatment of Hypertension," *Planta Medica*, vol. 85, no. 4, pp. 312–334, 2019, doi: 10.1055/a-0801-8771.
- [59] O. C. Obode, A. H. Adebayo, C. A. Omonhinmin, and O. F. Yakubu, "A systematic review of medicinal plants used in nigeria for hypertension management," *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2231–2276, 2020, doi: 10.31838/ijpr/2020.12.04.142.
- [60] S. B. Obakiro *et al.*, "Ethnobotany, ethnopharmacology, and phytochemistry of traditional medicinal plants used in the management of symptoms of tuberculosis in East Africa: A systematic review," *Tropical Medicine and Health*, vol. 48, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1186/s41182-020-00256-1.
- [61] P. Pant, S. Pandey, and S. Dall'Acqua, "The influence of environmental conditions on secondary metabolites in medicinal plants: a literature review," *Chemistry and Biodiversity*, vol. 18, no. 11, 2021, doi: 10.1002/cbdv.202100345.
- [62] H. Silva and R. Bárbara, "Exploring the anti-hypertensive potential of lemongrass—a comprehensive review," *Biology*, vol. 11, no. 10, 2022, doi: 10.3390/biology11101382.
- [63] F. K. Mediesse, T. Boudjeko, A. Hasitha, M. Gangadhar, W. F. Mbacham, and P. Yogeewari, "Inhibition of lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced neuroinflammatory response by polysaccharide fractions of *Khaya grandifoliola* (C.D.C.) stem bark, *Cryptolepis sanguinolenta* (Lindl.) Schltr and *Cymbopogon citratus* Stapf leaves in raw 264.7 macrophages and U87 glioblastoma cells," *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2018, doi: 10.1186/s12906-018-2156-2.

- [64] S. A. Adefegha, S. I. Oyeleye, and G. Oboh, "Distribution of phenolic contents, antidiabetic potentials, antihypertensive properties, and antioxidative effects of soursop (*Annona muricata* L.) fruit parts in vitro," *Biochemistry Research International*, vol. 2015, 2015, doi: 10.1155/2015/347673.
- [65] M. S. Subramanian, G. M. S. Nandagopal, S. A. Nordin, K. Thilakavathy, and N. Joseph, "Prevailing knowledge on the bioavailability and biological activities of Sulphur compounds from Alliums: A potential drug candidate," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 18, 2020, doi: 10.3390/molecules25184111.
- [66] T. Cui, W. Liu, S. Chen, C. Yu, Y. Li, and J. Y. Zhang, "Antihypertensive effects of allicin on spontaneously hypertensive rats via vasorelaxation and hydrogen sulfide mechanisms," *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 128, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2020.110240.
- [67] E. Idm'hand, F. Msanda, and K. Cherifi, "A review of moroccan medicinal plants used in the treatment of hypertension," *International Journal of Nature and Life Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 48–78, 2022, doi: 10.47947/ijnls.1010197.
- [68] T. Hamel, M. Zaafour, and M. Boumendjel, "Ethnomedical knowledge and traditional uses of aromatic and medicinal plants of the wetlands complex of the guerbes-sanhadja plain (Wilaya of Skikda in Northeastern Algeria)," *Herbal Medicine: Open Access*, vol. 04, no. 01, 2018, doi: 10.21767/2472-0151.100035.
- [69] J. S. Agapin, "Medicinal plants used by traditional healers in pagadian city, Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2020, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3625332.
- [70] P. K. Rao, S. S. Hasan, B. L. Bhellum, and R. K. Manhas, "Ethnomedicinal plants of Kathua district, J&K, India," *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 171, pp. 12–27, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2015.05.028.
- [71] A. Abubakar and M. Haque, "Preparation of medicinal plants: Basic extraction and fractionation procedures for experimental purposes," *Journal of Pharmacy And Bioallied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 1, 2020, doi: 10.4103/jpbs.JPBS_175_19.
- [72] H. G. Ong, S. M. Ling, T. T. M. Win, D.-H. Kang, J.-H. Lee, and Y.-D. Kim, "Ethnomedicinal plants and traditional knowledge among three Chin indigenous groups in Natma Taung National Park (Myanmar)," *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 225, pp. 136–158, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2018.07.006.
- [73] A. Bourqui *et al.*, "Hypertension treatment with *Combretum micranthum* or *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, as decoction or tablet: a randomized clinical trial," *Journal of Human Hypertension*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 800–808, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41371-020-00415-1.
- [74] H. Li *et al.*, "Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used by the Yi people in Mile, Yunnan, China," *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 22, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1186/s13002-024-00656-1.
- [75] A. N. M. Alamgir, "Herbal drugs: their collection, preservation, and preparation; evaluation, quality control, and standardization of herbal drugs," in *Therapeutic Use of Medicinal Plants and Their Extracts*, 2017, pp. 453–495. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-63862-1_10.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Meliza Parba is currently pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy in Biology at Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology (MSU-IIT) under DOST - ASTHRDP (Department of Science and Technology-Accelerated Science and Technology Human Resource Development Program). She also completed her bachelor's and master's degrees in Biology at the same school. She can be contacted at email: meliza.parba@g.msuiit.edu.ph.

Cesar G. Demayo is a professor emeritus at Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology with a Ph.D. in Entomology and Genetics from the University of the Philippines-Los Banos. His skills and expertise encompass computational biology, entomology, ethnomedicine, genetics, phylogenetic analysis, systematics, morphometrics, functional morphology, ecology, evolution, and biodiversity. He can be contacted at email: cgdemayo@gmail.com or cesar.demayo@g.msuiit.edu.ph.